

A BALANCED STRATEGY FOR EMPOWERMENT OF WOMEN TEACHERS

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Abstract:

Today we live in a world of sharp contrasts. There has been great progress in human life style and economic development. At the same time, deep-rooted social and political imbalances continue to constrain opportunities for many of the world's poor and marginalised, especially women. Women constitute nearly half of the population of the world. But, in spite of this fact they have never received requisite attention, rather many a time they have been neglected. Indian society is a multilingual, multicultural society subdivided by remarkable caste, creed and gender differences. In the chequered social system in India, women not only find themselves in variegated positions - both favourable and unfavourable but have to cope with the different social norms and traditions that have been framed through the ages. The empowerment of women is an essential precondition for the elimination of world poverty and the upholding of human rights. This concept is accompanied with, freedom, self-determination and power, which are necessary for the women all over the world. Since education and employment are key factors in empowerment of women in most of the societies, there is much theoretical and practical studies that stress educational and employment opportunities as critical means for women to attain control over their lives. But this does not realise in practical sense. Empowerment of working women has a positive impact on families as an income earner, a facilitator and a care taker of the children and other members of the family and also for the growth and development of the children of the schools. From gender equality perspective, empowering have a sustained impact on gender relations in the community and in society, at large. This paper is an attempt to quantify women empowerment with the help of a balanced empowerment strategy score.

Key Words: Empowerment of Women Teacher, Intrinsic Capability, Acquired Capability, Institutional Capability, Personal Accountability, School Accountability, Family Accountability, Capability- Accountability Equilibrium, Aggregate Capability Index, Aggregate Accountability Index & Balanced Empowerment Strategy.

1. Introduction:

Women constitute nearly one-half of the global population. However, the distribution of these numbers is not even throughout the globe. Women constitute around 70 per cent of the poverty-ridden population of the world (UNDP: 1995). Globally, women's participation in the labour market remained steady in the two decades from 1990 to 2010, floating around 52 per cent. In contrast, global labour force participation rates for men declined steadily over the same period, from 81 to 77 per cent. The share of women in the labour force gives an indication of the extent of women's access to the labour market relative to men's, a value of 50 percent indicating gender parity. Employment levels in the services sector continue to grow for both women and men. In the more developed economies, the labour force especially the female labour force is employed predominantly in services. This sector accounts for at least three quarters of women's employment in most of the more developed regions and in Latin America and the Caribbean. Over the years, women have entered various traditionally male-dominated occupations. However, they are still rarely employed in jobs with status, power and authority or in traditionally male blue-collar occupations. All over the world, women are more likely than men to be contributing family workers more than twice as likely in most regions .

Educational theories reveal that there is general acceptance regarding the significance of childhood experiences in the later development of a person. It is highly ironical that a woman who as a mother has always been regarded as the first teacher of the child is herself being left uneducated. Girls have a much lower access to education than boys do. Gender gaps are large and persistent; reasons are many and differ from one country to another and from one culture to another. The majority of the world's school dropout children are girls, in most parts of the world girls are underrepresented at the school level (UNESCO: 2009 a). As an attempt to address these unequal situations great stress is being given to increase the number of female teachers at the primary school level to provide the girls with role models, with whom they can identify in their formative years. Quality in education depends in large part on the quality of the teaching staff. Gender balance among the staff is critical for promoting gender parity and equality in access to, and achievement in, education and for creating a supportive and non discriminating learning environment for both women and men. There is evidence that gender balance among teaching staff is closely related to the improvement of gender parity in enrollments (Colclough and others: 2003). As the proportion of female teacher increases from low levels, girls' enrollment rise relative

to boys. The “feminisation” of the teaching profession, particularly in countries where women have lower socio economic status, can serve as an empowering tool for young women to pursue their studies and for parents to choose to educate girls (UNESCO: 2003).

	1999	2000	2009	2010	2014	2015
World	59.12	59.46	62.28	62.68	63.61	64.09
Developed Countries	81.43	81.53	82.42	82.86	83.16	83.23
Developing Countries	52.45	52.94	57.09	57.57	59.12	59.64
Africa	44.49	44.40	45.39	45.79	46.92	47.27
Asia	50.53	51.05	57.10	57.78	60.18	60.92
Europe	84.21	84.41	85.62	86.38	86.97	87.04
Northern America	78.27	78.72	79.62	79.53	79.42	79.64
India	35.59	35.59	-	-	49.49	49.49
China	-	-	56.76	57.55	60.98	62.60
Pakistan	-	44.90	46.47	47.72	49.61	50.37
Afghanistan	9.72	-	29.47	31.0	-	34.55
Sri Lanka	-	-	84.91	85.01	-	86.45
Low Income Countries	34.40	35.65	37.96	38.37	39.55	39.70
High Income Countries	79.45	79.62	80.45	80.85	80.95	81.00

Source: UNESCO Institute for Statistics (2017)

Above data displays, regional averages of women’s share in the teaching staff for different years, the trends shows that the participation of women in the teaching profession has increased in primary education in most countries. Women predominate in teaching at the primary level in most developed and high income countries, and their global share increased from 59 to 64 per cent between 1999 and 2015. In spite of the changes that have occurred in women’s participation in the labour market, women continue to bear most of the responsibilities for the home: caring for children and other dependent household members, preparing meals and doing other housework. In all regions, women spend at least twice as much time as men on unpaid domestic work. Women who are employed spend an inordinate amount of time on the double burden of paid work and family responsibilities; when unpaid work is taken into account, women’s total work hours are longer than men’s in all regions (Addati and Cassirer: 2008).

1.1 Research Problem: Empowerment of women teachers is an issue that has become increasingly important to Ministries of Education, Non-Governmental Agencies and other agencies supporting educational development and development of women in general. This is particularly because of the impact of a woman teacher on school children’s enrolment, educational achievement and development of younger generation. Empowerment of women teachers has a positive impact on families as an income earner, a facilitator and a care taker of the children and other members of the family and also for the growth and development of the children of the schools. From gender equality perspective, empowering women as teachers both in their family level and school level have a sustained impact on gender relations in the community and in society, at large. With the goal of empowering women teachers, development of the women in the society can be achieved through their interaction with the institutions for greater inclusion and cohesion. There is a need, therefore, to understand the empowerment of the Primary School Women Teachers (PSWT) of Kannur district in comparison with Primary School Men Teachers (PSMT) of Kannur district, on the basis of their capability differences and their accountability of achievement towards the two major institutions family and school. The present study attempts to find out the list of capabilities necessary to demonstrate the dimensions of empowerment of women teacher, within the existing institutional setup of Family and School and their accountability of achievement with the help of a Balanced Empowerment Strategy.

1.2 Objectives of the Study: The present study is guided by the following objectives.

- ✓ To examine the major determinants of Capability and Accountability of Primary School Women Teachers of Kannur district.
- ✓ To find out the level of Empowerment through Balanced Empowerment Strategy.

1.3 Scope of the Study: Education and work are the most important factors in the process of social, economic and political development of women. Education has assisted the breaking up of their economic and political isolation and has enabled them to participate in the wider economic and political process of the society. Even though the position of women in Kerala has improved dramatically according to ‘conventional indicators’ such as health status, literacy, education and life expectancy, and is even comparable to that of advanced countries, there has been no corresponding improvement in their social and economic status. Primary education, in the education sector of Kerala is the largest sector where women’s have the largest share more than 70 percent. The Eleventh Plan has focused on to bring out a considerable increase in the number of skill imparting institutions in the state with a considerable emphasise on gender auditing and gender budgeting. Gender auditing is concerned

with the assessment of the gender impact of policies and programmes not just in technical terms but also in terms of overcoming personal and institutional biases in the culture of the relevant organisations which hinder the achievement of gender equity objectives. The present study is a humble attempt to put forward a method of measuring empowerment and tracking changes in the level of empowerment.

1.4 Methodology of the Study: The methodology adopted in the present study is empirical and analytical. The area of the study is Kannur District, where the highest number of protected teachers were found with maximum number of uneconomic schools under the Kerala State. Generalisation is made on a comparative basis of primary data collected from both men and women teachers of the primary schools of Kannur. Out of total 1106 primary schools in Kannur district, concentration of female teachers is more than 60 percentage. More than 10% of the primary school teachers were selected for the present study by a stratified random sampling with appropriate weightage, as follows,

Management (State/ Central)	Male	Female	Total
Government Schools (State)	50	80	130
Aided Management Schools (State)	90	500	590
Unaided Schools (State)	10	55	65
Kendriya Vidyalaya (Central)	4	6	10
Total Number of Teachers	154	641	795

The primary data collected through a comprehensive, purposeful and structured survey method. A pre-tested interview schedule is used to meet the requirements of the study. Many of the qualitative responses are collected with the help of rating scales. Data analysis is done on two dimensional format, first from the capability side and next by obtaining an accountability index and finally by aggregating and obtaining a Balanced Empowerment Strategy Score.

2. Review of Literature:

At present there exist a plethora of studies on women empowerment and women's role in economic development. Women and their role in socio- economic and political development of the society and empowerment of women has been the subject matter of intensive research in recent period. Women in general and rural women in particular continue to constitute a single largest group of backward citizens in India who neither have access to power structure nor have any effective method to overcome their age old inequality and subordination. In the colonial period, when males were recruited for work in plantation etc. women were pushed in to subsistence production which kept the supply of male labour cheap, but worsened the position of women(Boserup:1990). Women are principal providers of care and support for infants and children and the role of women in the economy and their status in society is become a crucial factor for growth and development of the society (Mohanty and Tripathy: 2002) are being discriminated in terms of food in traditional societies (Kynch and Sen: 1983). In developing countries, women's future well being is often tied with that of their children, on whom they are dependent in their old age; therefore choices that reduce their current well being but improve their children's prospects further women's own interest. Such choices are both narrowly rational and self aware (Agarwal: 1994). The Govt. of India has continuously been formulating strategies and initiating process to bring women in to the mainstream. The alarming decline in women's participation highlighted in the report of the committee in the status of women in 1974 shifted the focus of attention to women's role in economic and political activity from the social aspects of women. After the declaration of women's decade in 1975-85, there was an upsurge in the theoretical as well as on empirical literature on women studies. Women issues come to the center of the development in the 1980's of India, a number of women empowerment programmers for women were formulated among which some where sponsored by the government to enhance literacy and skill that would be able to make women to deal with their environment from a position of strength (Gose:2002). Studies in the later eighties highlighted the employment among women has deteriorated over time, but trend in employment of women exhibited remarkable improvement in particular sectors and among particular social and economic classes (Mitra, Pathak and Mukherji:1980). Several factors have contributed to the creation of an atmosphere in which some middle class women in south India seek for employment, of many factors the most important factors urging women to join in gainful employment outside their home work are rising cost of living, inflation, consumerism, high cost of children's education, marriage and the concern for future security. Working wives have compartmentalised their work and domestic worlds much more than their husbands. This is becomes easy when work is defined by women primarily in terms of economic need, and not as the means of personal or carrier aspirations. A woman's decision to seek or not to seek paid work is complex and depends not just on economic need or educational skill, but on personal and contextual factors. A woman's paid work has not resulted in a universal change of attitudes towards gender related issues. Instead, it has becomes part of her obligation, thus nullifying the power of economic resources as an instrument to change in her domestic status (Ramu: 1989). In Kerala, educational status of parents and husbands has a direct influence on the female work participation and Kerala's female work participation rate is lower that of all India rate (Devi: 2002). As women increasingly gain occupational mobility, they are not only exposed to the same physical

hazards of work environment as men but also exposed to the pressures created by multiple role demands and conflicting expectations. They have stepped into work place but the role, responsibilities of women still remain the same, i.e., women may be a teacher, still the “nurturing” or “care giving” roles are considered much a part of feminine roles. The expansion of socially acceptable roles for women in the paid work force has come largely through adding on new responsibilities and possibilities to those already assigned to them, rather than through structural changes in social institutions or interpersonal relationships (O’Connell: 2005) and mothers cannot meet their ‘Public world obligation’ without being accused of neglecting their duties in the private domain (George and Maguire: 1998). Since the issues related to women are multi dimensional as evident from the literature reviewed, therefore, require further probing.

3. Theoretical Framework and Empirical Results:

Empowerment of the women teacher is an idea to maximise her utility that is arising from the utilisation of her available opportunities without or despite the various constraints arising from the existing structure and state of society. It contains process of gaining power in order to grab the opportunities and resources for the development of self and for removing all the hurdles and constraints in the way of one’s self actualisation. Empowerment is a moving state; it is a continuum that varies in degree of power. It is relative, she can move from an extreme state of absolute lack of power to the other extreme of having absolute power. The nature of the empowerment process determines its outcomes, it moves like an upward spiral. When women failed to reflect and act the way it is intent to be, a dis-empowerment happens, like a downward spiral that discourages women and thereby hinders all her efforts.

3.1 Major Concepts: The major concepts coined here to explain the empowerment of women teachers through capability and accountability frame work is,

Capability Accountability Equilibrium: The equilibrium point of Capability and Accountability, the tangency point of capability to function and accountability of achievement. At this point, Grand Capability Index and Grand Accountability Index are equal, and the differential score (A- C) is equal to zero. Any unbalance in this capability accountability may lead to disequilibrium or divergence in the process of empowerment.

Balanced Empowerment Strategy: A series of action or steps taken to achieve empowerment through the balance or equilibrium of Grand Capability and Grand Accountability. Balanced Empowerment Strategy is a process or path of the locus of combination of the equilibrium points of capability and accountability. Each point on this strategy line shows an empowered situation.

BES Score: Balanced Empowerment Strategy (BES) score, a differential score put forward here to analyse the process of empowerment through capability accountability equilibrium. This score is calculated by taking the difference between Grand Accountability Index and Grand Capability Index (BES SCORE = GAI- GCI). A zero BES score shows an empowered level with capability accountability equilibrium. A balanced empowerment strategy is obtained by connecting all the zero BES points plotted against time.

3.2 Measurement of Empowerment: The empowerment process is measured in two ways, by being and doing. The empowerment spiral by evaluating what they are, that’s the nature and the state of the women, as an agent of institution and also by measuring what they done, that is their outcome or achievement. The two way directional approach is introduced here in order to analyse women’s empowerment that must underlie institutional matters, they are;

- ✓ Capability of the Women
- ✓ Accountability of Women

The state of being is determined by her capabilities gives the identification of valuable functioning (choice embedded with freedom) that she want to do and to achieve with a satisfactory degree with range of opportunities. Accountability of the teacher helps to evaluate the achievement of the any activity arising out of the functioning. The functioning of the women teachers activities, her doing is subject to the nature of two major social institutions, Family and School, which are historically evolved, culturally developed, and also varies spatially and temporarily.

3.3 Capability of Women: Capability Approach relies on the assessment of 1) well being, and 2) the freedom to pursue ‘well-being’. The well being of a person can be seen in terms of the Quality (the ‘wellness’, as it where) of the women’s being. Living may be seen as consists of a set of interrelated ‘functioning’, consisting of beings and doings. Capability is, thus, a set of vectors of functioning, reflecting the women’s freedom to lead a type of life or another and also reflects the women’s freedom to choose from possible livings. The present study is based on the list of capabilities by Robeyns [2006], that are modified and applied to the present context by matching with the needs and requirements of the sample respondents and classified into the following three major sets. Each set consists a group of variable that are:

- ✓ Intrinsically Desirable, termed as Intrinsic Capability (IC)
- ✓ Instrumentally Significance, termed as Acquired Capability and (AC)
- ✓ Distributive Significance, termed as Institutional Capability (NC)

Each of the set of variables that are selected for the detailed analysis of the women teachers are listed as follows,

3.3.1 Capability Set 1 (Intrinsic Capability): Intrinsic means inherent and intrinsic capabilities means capabilities that are essential for the up bring and development of the individual that belongs to them naturally by birth, by gene, or by hereditary. Capability set 1 includes variables that are intrinsically desirable like,

- ✓ Early Childhood Variables and Present Environment : A person's well being, depends on a life, that is adequately nourished, having a decent shelter etc. and the perception of their present self has a deep rooted past, in which the things they possessed, shared and acknowledged along with other children also matters. Every Individual has a past life from her she gets enough mastering experience to look forward for a better future. Women as a home maker, she has the prime responsibility of the household, childcare and household management. Therefore here present household environment and the facilities available for her functioning is also comes under the intrinsic capability list.
- ✓ Physical Health: This capability explains being able to live a life of normal length in good health. The important factor in this capability set is the physical health of the individual, which is the integral part of their empowerment process.
- ✓ Mental Health: The major things that affect the individual capabilities that are intrinsically desirable are his or her mental capacities. Mental well being relates mainly to the absence of any negative mental status of being and doing, such as not being able to sleep, worrying or feeling depressed, lonely or restless etc.
- ✓ Personal Integrity: Integrity means moral uprightness that gives a feeling of wholeness and soundness in an individual's personality. Personal Integrity and Self worth is highly significant in capability functioning that is intrinsically desirable.
- ✓ Self Respect: This capability warrants inclusion of things that being respected and treated with dignity. This capability explains the self worth of her being as a human in co-existence with the others in the society with much cheerful high spirit, mutual respect they shown in almost all their dealings, leading a dignified life, striving for excellence and self fulfilling in everything they do and act
- ✓ Safety and Protection: Safety and Protection are important state of being. This capability adversely affected when women experiences all sources of personal violence such as physical attacks, domestic violence, crimes and sexual assault etc. This capability has a major gender dimension when women face all kinds of unequal treatment, discrimination and violence within the household and at the societal level.

3.3.2 Capability Set II (Acquired Capability): The second sets of capabilities are those abilities that are instrumentally significant that a person acquired, possessed or obtained through one's own effort during her life time. These are abilities that a person gained through her experience can acts as a tool or technique, or a dedicate thing that used to perform, control her existence for the derived level of outcome or action. With this acquired capabilities she can divert an adverse situation or circumstances in to a more pleasant and worthwhile. Capability set II includes variables that are instrumentally significant, it includes,

- ✓ Educational attainment: Educational attainment refers to the highest level of education an individual has completed. Rising educational attainment is a key mechanism for empowering woman.
- ✓ Skills: In recent decades, much of the improvement in human life is attributed through the diffusion of innovation skills and technological advancement; all these revolutionised the role of knowledge in the path of progress.
- ✓ Personal freedom: This capability explains women's power to act, speak, and think as one wants to without the hindrance or restraint by others with the permissible limit of law and order. Woman should have the right and privilege to protect their rights and to exercise their freedom to live and do her duties.
- ✓ Time and leisure: This capability refers to a range of techniques used to manage time when accomplishing specific tasks, and also spending their leisure to enhance their well being. The division of time and responsibility for paid up work, non paid up work at home, effective management of time for work and leisure with proper relaxation etc are comes under this.

3.3.3 Capability Set III (Institutional Capability): This capability is influenced by the Individual's, and his fellow being's, household, school and community characteristics that are inter related and coexisted in nature. Capability set III includes variables that are having distributive effect or significance that arising from the teachers interaction with the institutions includes variable like,

- ✓ Family Dynamics: These capabilities are arising from the women's interaction with her family, total members of the family, marital status of the respondent, number of children, and details of her domestic work etc. Family as a social institution, that shapes and modulates a person's perception and attitude can create far reaching consequences on her capabilities.
- ✓ Domestic Work: In spite of the changes that have occurred in women's participation in the labour market, women continue to bear most of the responsibilities for the home. Being a teacher and a member of the family, the teacher has do double role both for the paid up work for the school and also the non paid up domestic work at the household.

- ✓ School Dynamics: This capability explains women’s or men’s work especially related to the variables arising out of their interaction with school. This dynamism covers the teacher’s ability or process being involved by interacting with various school related activities on the basis of the management of school and location of their school etc.
- ✓ Paid up work : Paid up work gives a sense of freedom and self worth and by that a person can utilise the best of his or her well being for the betterment of himself or herself and the betterment of others related to them. The major variables coming under this capability are the designated post she holds on, her total years of service, etc.
- ✓ Income and Ownership of Assets: Income or salary from employment is a variable that directly act as a capability. The asset holding, earnings from other sources other than job, revenue generated by investment were all acts as a means and also an ends in teachers capability.
- ✓ Social Variables: Sometimes the root of women’s subjugation is seen in socio-political structure of the society. Discussing women in a social context, it should be important to note that they differs significantly in terms of their social environment, values, needs and interests. This variable analyse women’s active social attitudes and participation
- ✓ Political Variables: The variable of political integrity of the women acts as the next important capability item in the distributive aspects. This variable gives an idea about her political orientation, that she is leading an integrated political life with all the rights that envisaged in our society and protected by our constitution with much freedom embedded in it.

An aggregate Capability Index, termed as GRAND Capability Index is calculated by taking the summation of the three indices namely intrinsic, acquired and institutional capabilities. That is,

$$\text{Grand Capability Index} = \text{F (Intrinsic Capability Index, Acquired Capability Index, Institutional Capability Index)}$$

$$\text{G C I} = \text{I C I} + \text{A C I} + \text{N C I}$$

Where G C I - Aggregate Capability Index/ Grand Capability Index

The capability approaches a multi dimensional one, it facilitates interpersonal comparison of opportunities for achieving an empowered state of being is calculated by the Grand Capability Index and given in Table (3).

Index	I C I	A C I	N C I	G C I
Well Being (Mean Score = 4)	18 (2.81)		164 (25.59)	2 (0.31)
Moderately Well (Mean Score = 3)	549 (85.65)	115 (17.94)	169 (26.37)	328 (51.17)
Average (Mean Score = 2)	48 (7.49)	424 (66.15)	140(21.84)	241(37.6)
Poor (Mean Score = 1)	20 (3.12)	40 (6.24)	82(12.79)	53 (8.27)
Worst (Mean Score = 0)	6 (0.94)	62 (9.67)	86 (13.42)	17 (2.65)
TOTAL	641 (100.00)	641(100.00)	641 (100.00)	641 (100.00)

The grand capability Index gives the picture that really half of the total 641 female teachers, 51.17 percent placed in a moderately well being level, 37.6 percent are on average level and 10.92 percent below average level. Out of the total 10.92 percent below average people 2.65 percent have a worst level of being. Individual scores of PSWT regarding Intrinsic, Acquired and Institutional Capability proves that 25.59 percent are in well being in NCI, followed by ICI (2.81 percent). Women teachers have an inconsistent performance as far as Institutional Capability is concerned. Around 26.21 percent of teachers are below average level as far as NCI is concerned, followed by ACI with 15.91 percent and only 4.06 percent are placed in a low level of being with respect to ICI.

Index	I C I	A C I	N C I	G C I
Well Being (Mean Score = 4)	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	8 (5.19)	0 (0.0)
Moderately Well (Mean Score = 3)	121 (78.57)	102 (66.23)	29 (18.83)	70 (45.45)
Average (Mean Score = 2)	29 (18.83)	49 (31.82)	61 (39.61)	81 (52.6)
Poor (Mean Score = 1)	2 (1.3)	3 (1.95)	53 (34.42)	3 (1.95)
Worst (Mean Score = 0)	2 (1.3)	0 (0.0)	3 (1.95)	0 (0.0)
TOTAL	154 (100.00)	154(100.00)	154 (100.00)	154 (100.00)

The number of men teachers below the average level is maximum with respect to Institutional capability, 36.37 percent, followed by ICI 2.6 percent and ACI 1.95 percent. The Grand Capability Index of men teachers indicates that majority are in average level, 52.6 percent followed by a moderately well being level 45.45 percent. Only 1.95 percent are placed in less than average level. Compared to women, men are having a constant, consistent performance in over all capability indices (table 4). By comparing ICI and ACI and NCI, it is quite evident that 5.19 percent of the men teachers are in well being level in NCI. To further to know about

the variation of distribution of these indices among the teachers, co-efficient of variation is used and the estimated results are,

	Capability 1 (IC1)	Capability 2 (ACI)	Capability 3 (NCI)
Capability 1 (IC1)	0.2562 (0.3071)		
Capability 2 (ACI)	0.1813 (0.1668)	0.4897 (0.2076)	
Capability 3 (NCI)	0.2516 (0.1583)	0.5758 (0.1216)	1.7944 (0.5867)

Figures in parenthesis shows men's coefficient

Co-efficient of variation explains there is great dispersion or inequality in the distribution of capability set three, and for women that variability is much higher than men. Analysis shows that men are more consistent in their capability to function with less variability.

3.4 Accountability of Achievement of Women Teachers: Accountability is prevalent in every sphere of human life. Accountability as a concept simply means accounting of one's performance with respect to the responsibility bestowed on a person. This accounting process or the continuous evaluation of the achievement can be done by the person herself or by an authority or society as a task that can mold and shape the human as a developed, capable adult with an empowered self. Accountability of Achievement is prior based on the following:

- ✓ Delegation of responsibilities: A process of delegating an array of responsibilities towards self, home and school level.
- ✓ Performing: An act of functioning at three different layers, personal, home and school.
- ✓ Information: Regular, reliable and relevant information, a key to greater accountability. stems from the institutional linkage
- ✓ Enforceability: An act of strengthening the accountability by enhancing freedom, rights for effective use of means for improved functioning and supporting factors.

A relationship of accountability is between a 'Principal' and an 'Agent' that acts on behalf of the principal. Here the women teachers act as an agent of development on behalf of two principal, institutions Home and School. The accountability of the primary school women teacher is analysed on three layers as Personal Accountability, Accountability towards family and school.

- ✓ Personal Accountability (PA)
- ✓ Institutional Accountability towards Family (FA)
- ✓ Institutional Accountability towards School (SA)

One of the interesting thing to be noted here is that the variables of Accountability has a direct relation with her capabilities, that are listed below,

3.4.1 Accountability Set I (Personal Accountability): Personal or Individual accountability means be an individual, one acts as an agent of change towards one's own self. The items included in this lists is,

- ✓ Decisions taking on Personal Matters: Decision making a thought process of selecting a logical choice from available options.
- ✓ Personal Satisfaction: Personal Satisfaction indicates Fulfillments of one's wishes, expectations, or needs, or the pleasure derived from her various personal activities and personal decisions.
- ✓ Personal Spending: Expenses most are incurred for personal activities or spending that are considered mostly of personal nature, for health, education carrier etc.
- ✓ Financial Autonomy: This accountability explains financial independence or a state of having sufficient personal wealth to live in accordance with one's need without the interference of spouse or other
- ✓ Socialising Behaviour: Next important variable taken for the personal accountability calculation is the difficulties faced by women in actively participating in social events.
- ✓ Personal Dependency: Personal dependency in enhancing one's life situation shows lack freedom or lack of self reliance, both causes downward spiral in the empowerment process.

3.4.2 Accountability Set II (Family Accountability): Family life rests solidly on the shoulder of women in all societies. As a wife, parent, a care giver they take the prime responsibility for ensuring the proper functioning of the families and the provision for everyday care and maintenance. The major items analysed in this,

- ✓ Decisions taking on Family Matters: Decision making within the household related to childcare, family budgeting etc. determines a women's achievement as an active participant for the well being of her family.
- ✓ Hours of Domestic Work: Time allotted for household work.
- ✓ Average Monthly Spending for family: Expenses most are incurred for family activities or average money incurred for family per month.
- ✓ Financial Autonomy: Financial independence or a state of having sufficient personal wealth to do various activities within the household, especially for enhancing the living condition of the members of the family without the interference of spouse or other

- ✓ Disagreement with spouse: Lack of consensus or approval from partner or spouse can causes a downward spiral in the empowerment process.
- ✓ Access to Public Services for family welfare: Availability and accessibility of various institutions in the society can also help the women to enhance her contribution towards her family.

3.4.3 Accountability Set III (School Accountability): The major accountability of teacher is towards her institution that pay her each work at she done with much dedication is evaluated with proper accounts. Therefore as far as her work is concerned she is much alert and vigilant in this manner.

- ✓ Decisions taking on Academic Matters : Decision making within the household related to childcare, family budgeting etc. determines a women’s achievement as an active participant for the well being of her family
- ✓ Satisfaction in School related matters: Satisfaction arising out of the completion or fulfillments of various tasks, expectations, and needs, or the pleasure derived from her various activities and decisions on various academic or school related matters.
- ✓ Hours of Teaching: This variable explains average hours of teaching per day done by a teacher within school.
- ✓ Financial Assistance to School: Financial Assistance provided by the teacher towards the school like providing financial assistance to the needy children, purchasing teaching aids or necessities etc.
- ✓ Corrective mechanisms adopted in teaching and learning process: This item explains various remedial measures adopted by the teacher as a corrective mechanisms to enhance teaching learning process.

Aggregate Accountability Index termed as GRAND ACCOUNTABILITY INDEX is calculated by taking the sum total of accountability indices of teacher towards personal, family and school.

$$\text{Grand Accountability Index (GAI)} = \text{Personal Accountability Index} + \text{Family Accountability Index} + \text{School Accountability Index}$$

$$\text{GAI} = \text{PAI} + \text{FAI} + \text{SAI}$$

GAI - Grand Accountability Index

The Grand Accountability thus obtained by summing all the indices listed above are classified in to five groups ranging from a standardised mean score of 4 to zero (table 6).

Index	PAI	FAI	SAI	GAI
Well Being (Mean Score = 4)	-	2 (0.31)	-	-
Moderately Well (Mean Score = 3)	7 (1.09)	10 (1.58)	-	-
Average (Mean Score = 2)	317 (49.45)	144 (22.36)	50 (7.56)	128 (19.84)
Poor (Mean Score = 1)	211(32.92)	259 (40.16)	361 (56.22)	365 (56.85)
Worst (Mean Score = 0)	106 (16.54)	226 (35.59)	230 (36.22)	148 (23.31)
TOTAL	641 (100.00)	641 (100.00)	641 (100.00)	641 (100.00)

The Grand Accountability Index indicates that only 19.84 percent of the teacher have a score equal to the average level of accountability of achievement and a major percent comes under poor and worst category (80.16 percent). On the basis of accountability classification the least achievement is in SAI (92.44 percent) followed by FAI (75.75 percent) and PAI (49.46 percent). It is interesting to note that 0.31 percent of women teachers are placed in well being state only in their achievement towards family. The GAI calculation for men teachers (table 7) shows a better achievement to men than women.

Index	PAI	FAI	SAI	GAI
Well Being (Mean Score = 4)	-	-	-	-
Above Average (Mean Score = 3)	3 (1.95)	12 (7.79)	-	-
Average (Mean Score = 2)	58 (37.66)	78 (50.65)	20 (12.99)	44 (28.57)
Poor (Mean Score = 1)	87 (56.49)	47 (30.52)	111 (72.08)	104 (67.53)
Worst (Mean Score = 0)	6 (3.9)	17 (11.04)	23 (14.94)	6 (3.9)
TOTAL	154(100.00)	154(100.00)	154(100.00)	154 (100.00)

The GAI index of men teachers calculated from PAI, FAI and SAI shows that out of total 154 men teachers, 28.57 percent men are placed in average level. This is a much better percentage compared to women’s 19.84 percent. As per GAI comparison, men teachers who placed a level equal and above average level on PAI is 39.61 percent against women’s 50.54 percent. on FAI men has 58.44 percent against women’s 24.25 percent, on SAI its is 12.99 percent against women’s 7.56 percent. This comparison gives the impression that women fall behind in comparison with men in GAI and also their achievement within family and school.

The co-efficient of variation of Accountability Indices are calculated to find the inconsistency of men and women in their level of achievement (table 8).

	Accountability 1	Accountability 2	Accountability 3

	(PAI)	(FAI)	(SAI)
Accountability 1 (PAI)	0.1866 (0.3357)		
Accountability 2 (FAI)	0.1922 (- 0.0446)	0.7704 (0.2481)	
Accountability 3 (SAI)	0.1538 (0.0696)	0.5298 (0.0918)	0.7251 (0.4874)

Figures in parenthesis shows men's coefficient

Coefficient of variation is used to check the unequal distribution of score among the teachers shows that, the value 0.7704 of FAI and 0.7251 of SAI indicates that a low level of unequal achievement exists among the women teachers compared to the PAI of 0.1866. Coefficient for men makes it clear that, compared to women men's score do not have much variation with respect to PAI, FAI and SAI. There is a negative co variation between FAI and PAI of men. The Coefficient of Variation of GAI and GCI obtained from the study shows that men are more consistent in both criteria of empowerment than women.

3.5 Balanced Empowerment Strategy: Calculation of the Balanced Empowerment Strategy though the Capability-accountability equilibrium is done by two steps, first by calculating the Grand Capability index and Grand Accountability index. Empowerment as a continuous process to get power over, power to, and power in things, life and situations is achieved through the capabilities and the power to control or direct those capabilities in to accountability. This process of empowerment, course of action is done with the match making of the two elements namely capability and accountability. Thus for the process of empowering women, a balanced equilibrium should be attributed with capability and accountability frame work. There are four types of situation encountered with the respective differences in the scores ranging from 0 to 4. The differential score zero indicates that both are equal and a balanced empowerment is attained. Scores 1, 2 and 3 depicts disequilibrium of slight, moderate and severe imbalances in capability and accountability equilibrium score.

Strategy Score	PSWT	PSMT	Total
Balanced Empowerment Strategy Score (BES)	52 (8.11)	20 (12.99)	72
Slight Unbalanced Empowerment Strategy Score (SLUBES)	291 (45.4)	85 (55.19)	376
Moderate Unbalanced Empowerment Strategy Score (MUBES)	284 (44.31)	49 (31.82)	333
Sever Unbalanced Empowerment Strategy Score (SRUBES)	14 (2.18)	0 (0.00)	14
TOTAL	641 (100.00)	154 (100.00)	795

The table (9) illustrates that out of the 795 teachers only 9.06 percent of the teachers are in the balanced equilibrium of empowerment. 47.3 percent are in slight unbalanced state, 41.89 percent are in moderate level of unbalance and 1.76 percent are in severe unbalanced state with a differential score 3. It is well clear that majority of the teachers are unbalanced state of equilibrium of empowerment on the basis of Capability Accountability frame work. BES Score indicates more men are in a balanced state of empowerment strategy (12.99 percent) compared to women (8.11 percent). The divergence of accountability of achievement in accordance with their capability to function shows that women teachers should take more effort to increase their accountability of achievement.

4. Major Hurdles in Empowerment of Women Teachers:

The major reason for the an unbalanced strategy of disempowerment are,

- ✓ Low Accountability of Teachers towards School: Women teachers were scored well in finishing of lesson, punctuality etc. But their performance in extracurricular and organisational activities, cooperation with other fellow teachers and motivational skills etc. are valued with less appreciation.
- ✓ Work- Family Conflict: Work family conflicts acts as a major hurdle in women empowerment process. Most of the women teachers have work-family conflict that hampers their empowerment process.
- ✓ Lack of Financial Autonomy and Discrimination: Lack of financial autonomy and high level of dependency adversely affect women's empowerment process. There are chances of gender discrimination and unequal treatment within the household that tarnish herself image.
- ✓ Lack of Motivation and Support Mechanisms: Even though women are good in maintaining an integrated social life, many a time they failed to get enough support and motivation at the time of need and in difficult circumstances.
- ✓ Time Constraints: Women's paid up work and non paid up work at domestic level creates lots of adjustment in her time schedule.

5. Suggestions and Conclusion:

The following measures are suggested to attain a balanced empowerment of women at personal, family and institutional level.

Effective Delegation of Personal Responsibilities: Women teachers are suggested to enhance their life situations by undertaking the following measures at the personal level,

- ✓ Proper unbundling of responsibilities with proper time management and outcome oriented delegation.
- ✓ Facilitate capacity building at each level of her performance.
- ✓ Ensures her participation in decision making with full authority and freedom.
- ✓ Build Self confidence and Self esteem in women through constant motivation.
- ✓ Make her feel pride by valuing her work.

Enhance Work - Family Support and Enrichment Mechanism: An institutional approach is needed to enhance women's well being by the active interference of her family.

- ✓ Create an enabling environment that support women's empowerment and provide her adequate resources to operationalise her developmental objectives. Like, where to channelise her income and for what etc.
- ✓ Effective sharing of responsibilities and work by other fellow members in the family especially by men.
- ✓ Prevent crime and domestic violence against women within the family level.

Effective Use of Information at School level: School as the major social institution that she interferes, can act as a monitoring authority to enhance women teachers well being by,

- ✓ Collect regular, reliable and relevant information for strengthening women's accountability of achievement as a performance appraisal.
- ✓ Involvement of women in nontraditional task, in designing, developing and application of new technologies.
- ✓ Participation in community programs, productive enterprises, politics, arts etc. and there by increase her awareness about social & political rights and exercise her rights wherever necessary.
- ✓ Conduct training programmes for women empowerment.
- ✓ Facilitate women networks, publications, availability of women specific data and other relevant information.
- ✓ Equality through more consistent documentation and dissemination of experiences disaggregated by sex to influence policy formulation and operational activities through favourable media.

Enforcement of Women's Rights through Public Institutions and Policies:

- ✓ Incorporate gender sensitive legislation, policy discussion and action.
- ✓ Build an experience in facilitating policy dialogue that benefit from the interaction of Non Governmental Organisations and other people in the civil society to promote women's condition.
- ✓ Existence of women's organisation and increased number of women leaders at village, district and national level.
- ✓ Allocation of public funds to women's developmental projects and programmes.
- ✓ Prevent crime and violence against women at domestic, district, state and national level by building legal awareness and by strengthening law and order through police force and judiciary.

Empowerment doesn't taken place in vacuum. Women's state of powerlessness arising out of the combination and interaction of institutional factors can hasten and hinder empowerment process. Empowerment is not something which can be handed over to women. This is a process which involves sincerity, earnestness, capacity and capability on the part of both men and women in the society. By that way she can strengthen her accountability as a responsible, development oriented and fortunate individual.

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